

Appendix: Overview of Attacks

Attack the application logic	Attack the off-chain application logic	Certificate authority attack	(Davenport A., 2018)
		Coindash attack	(Chen et al., 2020)
		Collusion attack	(Piatkivskiy et al., 2017)
		Cryptojacking	(Carlin et al., 2020; Zimba et al., 2019a; Zimba et al., 2019b; Anita and Vijayalakshmi, 2019; Hong et al., 2018; Konoth et al., 2018; Saad et al., 2019c; Eskandari Shayan et al., 2018; Yulianto et al., 2019; Bijmans, 2019; Amin Kharraz, Zane Ma, Paul Murley, Charles Lever, Joshua Mason, Andrew Miller, Nikita Borisov, Manos Antonakakis, and Michael Bailey, 2019; Swedan et al., 2018; Pastrana and Suarez-Tangil, 2019)
		Ether delta attack	(Chen et al., 2020)
		Fake receipt	(He Ningyu et al., 2020)
		Fake tokens	(He Ningyu et al., 2020)
		Flood & lood attack	(Harris Jona and Zohar Aviv, 2020)
		Overlay network DoS	(Lee and Kim, 2020)
		Refund attack	(Conti et al., 2018; Rahouti et al., 2018; Shrivias et al., 2020)
		SQL-injection attack	(Anita and Vijayalakshmi, 2019; Lazarenko and Avdoshin, 2018)
		Call to the unknown	(Vivar et al., 2020; Shrivias et al., 2020; Mense and Flatscher, 2018)
	Delegate function exploit	(Wang et al., 2019b; Sayeed et al., 2020; Hasanova et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2020; Homoliak et al., 2020)	
	EVM randomness exploit	(Wang et al., 2019b; Chen et al., 2020; Homoliak et al., 2020)	
	Exception disorder vulnerability exploit	(Sambana et al., 2020; Hasanova et al., 2019; Luu et al., 2016; Vivar et al., 2020; Homoliak et al., 2020; Zhu et al., 2018; Demir M., 2019; Mense and Flatscher, 2018; Chen et al., 2020)	
	Fake deposit exploit	(Ji Ru et al., 2020)	
	Gasless send exploit	(Vivar et al., 2020; Prechtel et al., 2019; Feng et al., 2019; Daojing He et al., 2020; Shrivias et al., 2020; Demir M., 2019; Mense and Flatscher, 2018)	
	Immutable bugs exploit	(Hasanova et al., 2019; Shrivias et al., 2020; Vivar et al., 2020; Homoliak et al., 2020; Praitheeshan et al., 2020; Mense and Flatscher, 2018)	
	Multiple withdrawal attack	(Rahimian et al., 2019)	
	Permission check exploit	(He Ningyu et al., 2020)	
Reentrancy vulnerability attack	(Li et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2019b; Sayeed et al., 2020; Hasanova et al., 2019; Lazarenko and Avdoshin, 2018; Moubarak et al., 2018; Luu et al., 2016; Vivar et al., 2020; Kiffer et al., 2017; Chen et al., 2020; Homoliak et al., 2020; Proper H., Stirna J., 2019; Saad et al., 2019c; 2020; Praitheeshan et al., 2020; Chinen Yuichiro et al., 2018; Fatima Samreen N., 2020; Zhao et al., 2017; Zhu et al., 2018; Feng et al., 2019; Jonathan and Sari, 2019;		

			Shrivas et al., 2020; Sayadi et al., 2018; Demir M., 2019; Mense and Flatscher, 2018)
		Rollback vulnerability exploit	(He Ningyu et al., 2020)
		Self-destruction attack	(Praitheeshan et al., 2020; Homoliak et al., 2020; Chen Jiachi et al., 2020; Demir M., 2019)
		Timestamp dependence exploit	(Sayeed et al., 2020; Luu et al., 2016; Chen et al., 2020; Homoliak et al., 2020; Praitheeshan et al., 2020; Zhu et al., 2018; Feng et al., 2019; Daojing He et al., 2020; Shrivas et al., 2020; Sayadi et al., 2018; Morganti et al., 2018; Demir M., 2019; Mense and Flatscher, 2018)
		Tx.origin vulnerability exploit	(Mense and Flatscher, 2018; Proper H., Stirna J., 2019)
		Unbounded operations exploit	(Demir M., 2019; Praitheeshan et al., 2020)
		Vulnerable multisig exploit	(Praitheeshan et al., 2020; Destefanis et al., 2018)
Attack the client application/ wallet		Dictionary attack	(Rahouti et al., 2018)
		Ether stealing attack	(Cheng et al., 2019)
		Flawed key generation exploit	(Shrivas et al., 2020)
		Private key retrieval attack	(Shrivas et al., 2020; Saad et al., 2019c; Morganti et al., 2018)
		RPC API exploit	(Thanh Bui et al., 2019; Praitheeshan et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2018b)
		Wallet malware attack	(Lazarenko and Avdoshin, 2018; Wang et al., 2018a; Rahouti et al., 2018; Homoliak et al., 2020; Conti et al., 2018)
		Wallet availability attack	(Homoliak et al., 2020)
		Wallet phishing	(Wang et al., 2018a; Lazarenko and Avdoshin, 2018; Hasanova et al., 2019; Averin A., 2019; Oksiiuk and Dmyreiva)
Attack the consensus mechanism		Alternative history attack	(Ghosh et al., 2020; Conti et al., 2018; Rahouti et al., 2018; Kiktenko O. et al., 2019; Vokerla et al., 2019; Sayadi et al., 2018; Morganti et al., 2018)
		Block discarding attack	(Tosh et al., 2017; Liang Xueping et al., 2018; Khoshavi et al., 2019)
		Block withholding attack	(Ghosh et al., 2020; Lee and Kim, 2019; Gao et al., 2019b; Chang et al., 2019; Chang and Park, 2019; Alkalay-Houlihan and Shah, 2019; Zamyatin et al., 2017; Teutsch et al., 2016; Conti et al., 2018; Rahouti et al., 2018; Tosh et al., 2017; Homoliak et al., 2020; Saad et al., 2019c; Solat Siamak and Potop-Butucaru Maria, 2017; Liang Xueping et al., 2018; Zhu et al., 2019; Shalini and Santhi, 2019; Vokerla et al., 2019; Qin R., 2020; Khoshavi et al., 2019; Hu et al., 2016; Shrivas et al., 2020; Kwon et al., 2017; Sarker et al., 2019; Dong et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2019a; Zhu et al., 2018)
		Bribery attack	(Hasanova et al., 2019; Deirmentzoglou et al., 2019; Bonneau, 2016; Conti et al., 2018; Rahouti et al., 2018; Homoliak et al., 2020; Averin A., 2019; Soni and Maheshwari, 2018; Shrivas et al., 2020)
		Changing systems parameters	(Hasanova et al., 2019)
		Double spend attack	(Ghosh et al., 2020; Zhang and Lee, 2019; Hasanova et al., 2019; Suliyanti and Sari, 2019; Zhang and Preneel,

		2019; Wang et al., 2019a; Deirmentzoglou et al., 2019; Ekparinya et al., 2018; Moubarak et al., 2018; Teutsch et al., 2016; Xu, 2016; Conti et al., 2018; Rahouti et al., 2018; Abd Halim, Norul Suhaliana Bt et al., 2017; Tosh et al., 2017; Chen et al., 2020; Homoliak et al., 2020; Zhu et al., 2018; Zaghoul Ehab et al., 2019; Peng Zhiniang and Chen Yuki, 2018; Bissias George et al., 2016; Rosenfeld, 2014; Jang Jehyuk and Lee Heung-No, 2019; Averin A., 2019; Sai and Tipper, 2019; Nicolas et al., 2019; Shalini and Santhi, 2019; Vokerla et al., 2019; Ramezan and Leung, 2020; Soni and Maheshwari, 2018; Zhang and Lee, 2020; Shrivastava et al., 2020; Sayadi et al., 2018; Morganti et al., 2018; Chaudhary et al., 2020; Ghassan O. Karame et al., 2015; Gervais, 2015; Amin Kharraz, Zane Ma, Paul Murley, Charles Lever, Joshua Mason, Andrew Miller, Nikita Borisov, Manos Antonakakis, and Michael Bailey, 2019; Saad et al., 2019c)
	Finney attack	(Ghosh et al., 2020; Conti et al., 2018; Rahouti et al., 2018; Saad et al., 2019c; Zaghoul Ehab et al., 2019; Averin A., 2019; Vokerla et al., 2019; Shrivastava et al., 2020; Morganti et al., 2018; Chaudhary et al., 2020)
	Fork after withholding	(Ghosh et al., 2020; Sarker et al., 2019; Chang et al., 2019; Chang and Park, 2019; Wang et al., 2019a; Conti et al., 2018; Rahouti et al., 2018; Zhu et al., 2018; Shalini and Santhi, 2019; Hu et al., 2016; Shrivastava et al., 2020; Kwon et al., 2017)
	Frontrunning attack	(Luu et al., 2016; Chen et al., 2020; Praitheeshan et al., 2020; Zhu et al., 2018; Eskandari Shayan et al., 2019; Sayadi et al., 2018; Demir M., 2019; Mense and Flatscher, 2018)
	Gas limit block stuffing	(Chen et al., 2020; Demir M., 2019)
	Goldfinger attack	(Ghosh et al., 2020)
	Grinding attack	(Homoliak et al., 2020)
	Incorrect transaction attack	(Luu et al., 2015)
	Long range attack	(Deirmentzoglou et al., 2019; Gazi et al., 2018; Homoliak et al., 2020; Zhang and Lee J.-H., 2019)
	Majority attack	(Ghosh et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2020; Li et al., 2020; Hasanova et al., 2019; Anita and Vijayalakshmi, 2019; Lazarenko and Avdoshin, 2018; Shrestha and Nam, 2019; Deirmentzoglou et al., 2019; Gao et al., 2018; Ye et al., 2018; Moubarak et al., 2018; Keenan, 2017; Teutsch et al., 2016; Xu, 2016; Liu et al., 2019; Rahouti et al., 2018; Homoliak et al., 2020; Proper H., Stirna J., 2019; Saad et al., 2019c; Zaghoul Ehab et al., 2019; Averin A., 2019; Liang Xueping et al., 2018; Jonathan and Sari, 2019; Shah and Sridaran, 2019; Khoshavi et al., 2019; Soni and Maheshwari, 2018; Cilloni T., 2020; Oksiuk and Dmyreiva; Shrivastava et al., 2020; Sayadi et al., 2018; Morganti et al., 2018; Hsieh, 2016; Wei et al., 2019)
	Nothing-at-stake attack	(Homoliak et al., 2020)
	Pool hopping attack	(Singh et al., 2019; Zamyatin et al., 2017; Rahouti et al., 2018; Homoliak et al., 2020; Zhu et al., 2019; Shrivastava et al., 2020)
	Punitive & feather forking	(Sambana et al., 2020; Hasanova et al., 2019; Zhang and Preneel, 2019; Winzer et al., 2019; Deirmentzoglou et

		al., 2019; Conti et al., 2018; Rahouti et al., 2018; Homoliak et al., 2020; Soni and Maheshwari, 2018; Magnani et al., 2018)
	Quantum attack	(Aggarwal et al., 2017; Proper H., Stirna J., 2019; Khalifa et al., 2019)
	Race attack	(Ghosh et al., 2020; Zhang and Lee, 2019; Hasanova et al., 2019; Suliyanti and Sari, 2019; Zhang and Preneel, 2019; Wang et al., 2019a; Deirmentzoglou et al., 2019; Ekparinya et al., 2018; Moubarak et al., 2018; Teutsch et al., 2016; Xu, 2016; Conti et al., 2018; Rahouti et al., 2018; Abd Halim, Norul Suhaliana Bt et al., 2017; Tosh et al., 2017; Chen et al., 2020; Homoliak et al., 2020; Zhu et al., 2018; Zaghoul Ehab et al., 2019; Peng Zhiniang and Chen Yuki, 2018; Bissias George et al., 2016; Rosenfeld, 2014; Jang Jehyuk and Lee Heung-No, 2019; Averin A., 2019; Sai and Tipper, 2019; Nicolas et al., 2019; Shalini and Santhi, 2019; Vokerla et al., 2019; Ramezan and Leung, 2020; Soni and Maheshwari, 2018; Zhang and Lee, 2020; Shrivastava et al., 2020; Sayadi et al., 2018; Morganti et al., 2018; Chaudhary et al., 2020; Ghassan O. Karame et al., 2015; Gervais, 2015)
	Resource exhaustion attack	(Luu et al., 2015; Kanjalkar et al., 2019)
	Selfholding attack	(Dong et al., 2019; Gao et al., 2019b)
	Selfish Mining	(Ghosh et al., 2020; Li et al., 2020; Chicarino et al., 2020; Anita and Vijayalakshmi, 2019; Zhang and Preneel, 2019; Wang et al., 2018a; Deirmentzoglou et al., 2019; Teutsch et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2019; Conti et al., 2018; Rahouti et al., 2018; Tosh et al., 2017; Chen et al., 2020; Homoliak et al., 2020; Proper H., Stirna J., 2019; Saad et al., 2018a; Zhu et al., 2018; Eyal Ittay and Gun Emin, 2014; Liang Xueping et al., 2018; Zhu et al., 2019; Nicolas et al., 2019; Shalini and Santhi, 2019; Vokerla et al., 2019; Soni and Maheshwari, 2018; Nayak et al., 2016; Azimy H., 2019; Eyal I., 2015; Shrivastava et al., 2020; Sayadi et al., 2018; Kwon et al., 2017; Gervais, 2015; Wei et al., 2019; Gao et al., 2018)
	Splitting attack	(Kovalchuk et al., 2017)
	Tradeoff attack	(Dinur and Nadler, 2017)
	Triangle attack	(Wang Y., 2019)
	Vector 76 attack	(Ghosh et al., 2020; Conti et al., 2018; Rahouti et al., 2018; Zaghoul Ehab et al., 2019; Averin A., 2019; Shrivastava et al., 2020; Morganti et al., 2018; Chaudhary et al., 2020)
Attack the P2P network	Balance attack	(Li et al., 2020; Ekparinya et al., 2018; Natoli and Gramoli, 2017; Chen et al., 2020; Saad et al., 2019c; Natoli Christopher and Gramoli Vincent, 2016; Shrivastava et al., 2020; Sayadi et al., 2018)
	BGP hijacking	(Li et al., 2020; Ekparinya et al., 2018; Apostolaki et al., 2017; Conti et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2020; Homoliak et al., 2020; Saad et al., 2019c; Ekparinya Parinya et al., 2019; Saad et al., 2019a; Shrivastava et al., 2020; Morganti et al., 2018)
	DDoS attack	(Sambana et al., 2020; Hasanova et al., 2019; Anita and Vijayalakshmi, 2019; Wang et al., 2018a; Saad et al., 2019b; Amooron and Rocha, 2019; Deirmentzoglou et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2018c; Moubarak et al., 2018; Saad et al., 2018b; Liu et al., 2019; Conti et al., 2018;

		Rahouti et al., 2018; Abd Halim, Norul Suhaliana Bt et al., 2017; Chen et al., 2020; Homoliak et al., 2020; Saad et al., 2019c; Saad Muhammad et al., 2020; Mirkin Michael et al., 2020; Zaghoul Ehab et al., 2019; Averin A., 2019; Paavolainen et al., 2018; Shalini and Santhi, 2019; Wu et al., 2020; Abhishta Abhishta, Reinoud A.M.G. Joosten, Sergey Dragomiretskiy, Lambertus Johannes Maria Nieuwenhuis, 2019; Soni and Maheshwari, 2018; Shrivastava et al., 2020; Morganti et al., 2018; Marella, 2017; Mense and Flatscher, 2018; Rodrigues and Stiller, 2019)
	Deanonymization attack	(Conti et al., 2018; Homoliak et al., 2020; Proper H., Stirna J., 2019; Zhu et al., 2018; Davenport A., 2018; Zhang et al., 2020; Shah and Sridaran, 2019)
	Delay attack	(Yuan et al., 2020; Moubarak et al., 2018; Averin A., 2019; Walck M. et al., 2019; Morganti et al., 2018; Gervais, 2015)
	DNS attack	(Shrivastava et al., 2020; Rahouti et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2020; Homoliak et al., 2020; Saad et al., 2019c; Davenport A., 2018; Liang Xueping et al., 2018; Ramdas and Muthukrishnan, 2019; Conti et al., 2018)
	Dust attack	(Wang et al., 2018c)
	Eclipse attack	(Li et al., 2020; Xu et al., 2020; Zhang and Lee, 2019; Hasanova et al., 2019; Anita and Vijayalakshmi, 2019; Swathi et al., 2019; Henningsen et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2019a; Deirmentzoglou et al., 2019; Moubarak et al., 2018; Conti et al., 2018; Rahouti et al., 2018; Abd Halim, Norul Suhaliana Bt et al., 2017; Tosh et al., 2017; Chen et al., 2020; Homoliak et al., 2020; Saad et al., 2019c; Zhu et al., 2018; Zaghoul Ehab et al., 2019; Alangot Bithin et al., 2020; Bissias George et al., 2016; Rajab Tayebbeh et al., 2020; Averin A., 2019; Liang Xueping et al., 2018; Jonathan and Sari, 2019; Shalini and Santhi, 2019; Vokerla et al., 2019; Soni and Maheshwari, 2018; Zhang and Lee, 2020; Nayak et al., 2016; Shrivastava et al., 2020; Morganti et al., 2018; Yves-Christian et al., 2018)
	Liveness denial	(Deirmentzoglou et al., 2019)
	Packet sniffing	(Morganti et al., 2018)
	Ransomware network attack	(Hasanova et al., 2019; Rahouti et al., 2018; Gurcan Cuneyt et al., 2019; Paquet-Clouston et al., 2019)
	Routing attack	(Apostolaki et al., 2017; Conti et al., 2018; Rahouti et al., 2018; Homoliak et al., 2020; Zaghoul Ehab et al., 2019; Apostolaki Maria et al., 2018; Saad et al., 2019a; Shrivastava et al., 2020; Morganti et al., 2018)
	Spam attack	(Paavolainen et al., 2018)
	Sybil attack	(Li et al., 2020; Xu et al., 2020; Zhang and Lee, 2019; Hasanova et al., 2019; Anita and Vijayalakshmi, 2019; Swathi et al., 2019; Henningsen et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2019a; Deirmentzoglou et al., 2019; Moubarak et al., 2018; Conti et al., 2018; Rahouti et al., 2018; Abd Halim, Norul Suhaliana Bt et al., 2017; Tosh et al., 2017; Chen et al., 2020; Homoliak et al., 2020; Proper H., Stirna J., 2019; Saad et al., 2019c; Zhu et al., 2018; Zaghoul Ehab et al., 2019; Alangot Bithin et al., 2020; Bissias George et al., 2016; Rajab Tayebbeh et al., 2020; Averin A., 2019; Liang Xueping et al., 2018; Jonathan and Sari, 2019; Shalini and Santhi, 2019; Vokerla et al., 2019; Soni and

		Maheshwari, 2018; Zhang and Lee, 2020; Nayak et al., 2016; Shrivasa et al., 2020; Morganti et al., 2018)
	Timejacking attack	(Moubarak et al., 2018; Conti et al., 2018; Homoliak et al., 2020; Saad et al., 2019c; Zaghoul Ehab et al., 2019; Shrivasa et al., 2020; Morganti et al., 2018)
Attack the VM/ language	DoS with (unexpected) revert	(Chen et al., 2020; Demir M., 2019)
	Forcible balance transfer	(Saad et al., 2019c)
	Keeping secrets exploit	(Vivar et al., 2020; Mense and Flatscher, 2018)
	Overflow attack	(Li et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2019b; Sayeed et al., 2020; Gao et al., 2019a; Sun and Yu, 2020; Chen et al., 2020; Homoliak et al., 2020; Saad et al., 2019c; Praitheeshan et al., 2020; Feng et al., 2019; Daojing He et al., 2020; Shrivasa et al., 2020; Demir M., 2019)
	Replay attack	(Anita and Vijayalakshmi, 2019; Chen et al., 2020; Proper H., Stirna J., 2019; Saad et al., 2019c)
	Short address attack	(Sayeed et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2019b; Chen et al., 2020; Saad et al., 2019c; Averin A., 2019; Shrivasa et al., 2020)
	Stack size exploit	(Vivar et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2020; Praitheeshan et al., 2020; Zhu et al., 2018)
	Transaction malleability	(Khan et al., 2020; Sayeed et al., 2020; Hasanova et al., 2019; Lazarenko and Avdoshin, 2018; Conti et al., 2018; Rahouti et al., 2018; Abd Halim, Norul Suhaliana Bt et al., 2017; Zhu et al., 2018; Averin A., 2019; Liu et al., 2017; Shrivasa et al., 2020; Morganti et al., 2018)
	Underflow attack	(Wang et al., 2019b; Sayeed et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2020; Homoliak et al., 2020; Praitheeshan et al., 2020; Daojing He et al., 2020; Shrivasa et al., 2020; Demir M., 2019)
	Opcod exploit	(Hasanova et al., 2019)

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